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SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOAL 13 (CLIMATE ACTION) AND ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY: AN INTERROGATION OF NIGERIA'S NATIONALLY DETERMINED CONTRIBUTION IN ADDRESSING CLIMATE CHANGE (2012-2022)

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17064110>

Abstract: This is a critical empirical look at Sustainable Development Goal 13 (climate action) and environmental sustainability: An interrogation of Nigeria's Nationally Determined Contribution in Addressing Climate Change 2012-2022. Particularly this research seeks to ascertain whether Sustainable Development Goal 13 on Climate Action tackled the problems of climate change from 2012- 2022. Furthermore the research discusses extensively how Nigeria's Nationally Determined Contribution prevented local environmental challenges from 2012 to 2022. Adopting a case study research design and documentary method of data collection from secondary sources, the value belief norm and the contingency theories explicitly explains the theories objectively. In the findings, Sustainable Development Goal 13 on Climate Action tackled the problems of climate change and Nigeria's Nationally Determined Contribution prevented local environment challenges. In furtherance to the research, the reason NDC's did not prevent local environment challenges is intrinsic on its weak execution by the government of Nigeria. The research concludes and recommends admits other things that Nigeria needs to strengthen its institutions, the National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (NESREA) and Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) commissioned to implement environmental laws in Nigeria.

Keywords: Sustainable Development Goal 13 (SDG 13), Climate Action, Nigeria's Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC), Environmental Sustainability, Climate Change Mitigation.

Introduction

The world is changing at an alarming rate and there has never been a time as decisive as of now that we need to address the uncertainties of these untimely effects of climate change. (Fuso-Nerini, et al, 2019). The attention of the United Nations has been drawn to see the rising need to collaborate and involve stakeholders to curtail this menace of climate change. In the year 2000, Millennium Development Goals had 8 objective Goals of which

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Goal 7 ensures environmental sustainability. Sustainable Development Goals was adopted in 2015, by United Nations members aimed at globally ensuring peace and prosperity for people and planet. The 17 SDGs while setting about climate change and working to preserve oceans and forests, highlighted the connections between the environmental, social and economic aspects of sustainable development. Sustainability is at the focus of the SDGs. Meanwhile, Sustainability implies optimally developing the goals of nations, societies and communities that must be attain in other to address sustainability by leading productive lives in a sustainable world through attempts to safeguard the environment, particularly by managing its natural resources, consuming and producing in a sustainable manner, and acting quickly to combat climate change. Officially the Agenda 2030, took center stage on transformative plans of action to address global challenges for the next 15 years (Flood, et al, 2022). The proposition of this and other similar objectives of the SDG is simply saying: Conservation of the environment must go hand in hand with natural environmental justice and justice for Climate Change (Nordas, & Gleditch, 2007). With a list of other sustainable goals, this research will heavily be hinged on SDG 13 climate action.

The United Nations Conference on Sustainable Development (UNCSD), in 2012 was established to set global goals in relation to economic, political, and environmental challenges we experience as a globe (Unsdg, 2015). From 2015 to 2030 SDG's has been projected as worldwide climate objectives committed to deal with strategic world's most sort after issue which is addressing climate change in relation to sustainability. This universal call to action involves a significant effort to combat the threat of climate change in a sustainable manner. It therefore influences how we manage our delicate natural resources by sustaining inclusive societies to reduce the inequalities faced by unfortunate communities and to support the prosperity of national economies (United Nations Sustainable Rapoteiree 2016). The SDG, is geared towards the 2030 agenda as a model for a mutual wealth in an environmentally sound planet where everybody gains and has an equal fair share from this agenda and that no one is left out - prosperity is shared in a sustainable future where everyone can live fulfilling lives in harmony with the environment. When we pay attention to addressing sustainability, we conjure intentional efforts to prevent environmental damage, particularly by managing the planet's natural resources responsibly, using and producing less, and acting quickly to combat climate change in order to meet the demands of future generations (sdgs.un.org, 2015). Measures to which Goal 13 Climate Action further enhances its roles in addressing climate change in this study is to: implement the UNFCCC to a goal of commitment made by developed country parties of mobilizing together \$100 billion yearly by 2020 from all sources to address the needs of developing countries in the context of meaningful mitigation actions and transparency on implementation; strengthen resilience in the face of climate change, improve adaptive capacity to subdue climate related hazards and natural disasters in all countries; examine how climate change measures are incorporated into national policies, strategies, and planning; and fully operationalize the Green Climate Fund through its capitalization as soon as possible, to encourage strategies that will increase the ability of developing countries and small island developing states to effectively plan for and manage the effects of climate change, with particular emphasis on women, youth, and marginalized communities (un.org, 2023).

The purpose of this study is to determine the connection between SDG 13 Climate Action and Environmental Sustainability and interrogates how Nigeria is purposeful in addressing climate change in Nigeria. This study further examines the need to address climate change in the country, judging from the fact that there is so much

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the environment has undertaken. With regards the cutting down of emissions and how the world continues to evolve climatically, and to commission guidelines and polices Nigeria should use, in addressing climate change, in other to understand how other nations are implementing their guided polices in addressing climate related issues that is currently facing the world.

The problem of the study arises from the pressing concern of climate change caused by emission of Green House Gases causing harm on the environment which further aggravates the outcome of climate change now and in the future. The UN, Stockholm declaration, Kyoto protocol and Paris Agreement have set out universal guidelines stipulated to safeguard the environment for sustainable solutions to be principally upheld and properly regulate environmental initiations in helping developing countries carry out their obligations especially towards the environment.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework of this study is anchored on two theories, Contingency theory and Value Belief Norm Theory. Value Belief Norm Theory postulated by Paul C. Stern *et al* in their 1999 publication titled, “*A value – Belief-Norm Theory of Support for Social Movement: The Case of Environmentalism*”, with contributions and modification by other scholars like Schwartz (1977; 1994), Van Lire (1987); Dunlap (1992); and Bilsky (1987); Value Belief Norm Theory, believes pro-environmental actions happens in response to individuals, whose morality towards the environment, are fortified in persons who acclaim that, deplorable environmental conditions causes a serious threat to other people and being conscious of the consequences of certain human actions towards the environment and could prevent those adverse consequences of being self-responsible. Scholars like (Black 1978; Van Liere and Dunlap 1978; Stern and Elworth 1985; Stern, Dietz and Black 1986; Stern, Dietz and Kalof 1993; Guagnano, Dietz and Stern 1994; Guagnano 1995; Guagnano, Stern and Dietz 1995; Stern, Dietz, Kalof and Guagnano 1995; Widegren 1998) argue extensively about supportive evidence which comes from studies focused on a variety of proenvironmental actions. Assumptions of the VBN theory is benched on three assumptions which are:

Moral Norm Activation, assumed by S.H Schwartz’s (1977), says that personal or organsational morality about proenvironmental actions take place to correct poor environmental practices in the societies. These actions are however, brought to light in persons, groups or organizations who have deep belief in pro-environmental actions, and to create a sense of awareness and education to non-believers, that the unsustainable conditions of the environment, with its attendant consequences, poses a threat to the environment and people so that initiated actions could prevent those consequences.

Contingency theory Proposed by an Austrian Psychologist Fred Edward Fielder in his 1964 Article titled, “*A Contingency Model of Leadership Effectiveness*”.

Contingency theory states that there is no single or ideal way to make decision in an organization, society or state and that all ways of organizing and making decision are not equally successful in any given circumstances. This implies that there is no optimum method for forming a corporation, group or organization. In other words this theory doesn’t stick to a particular model or process of making decisions in an organisations, state or society.

The assumptions of the theory is hinged on the three basic principle which are: Different leadership styles calls for different methods of adoption in certain decision making process. This means that there are no best ways of

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doing things, in other words different situations calls for different ways or approaches to handle, manage and solve group or organisational issues concerned.

Personality or trait of a leader will certainly determine how a leader would handle a particular situation. It therefore means that contingency theory shows a relationship between leadership effectiveness, style of leadership and situational circumstances.

A particular leadership style must match the circumstances in order to be effective, in view of this style, one can be able to determine whether they are the right leader for the particular situation.

In applying this theory, Nigerian has experienced mirage successive leadership of unprecedented democratic rule with systems of government in Nigeria since 2012 and still counting. She has recorded a huge mile stone with regards issues pertaining to the environment. In 2012, Nigeria recorded a significant change on leadership by the then President Goodluck Ebele Azikiwe Jonathan, which had little to contribute towards the sustainability of the environment, this indicated the type of leadership style his administration proffered. In 2013, the leadership style adopted by the then Nigerian government involving sustainable development and environmental issues was suitable to the circumstances of the Nigerian government as at that time. The leadership of Nigeria is crippled and handicapped when matters pertaining to serious adjustments on climate change is reserved adequate address. Over the years, there has been an instability in the mode of leadership in Nigeria system of government, which is why varied styles of leadership has resulted to addressing divergent climate change situation in the country.

Evidently, Nigeria has failed to observant about the adverse effects of climate change and she seems vulnerable, ranking the most 7th vulnerable in the world. The prognosis is, if Nigeria fails to adequately fortify herself to climate change by 2050, this will cause a huge fraction in the leadership style and will significantly be seen in an unfavorable situational style adopted by Nigerian leaders. The Federal Government's adaptation policies, laws, frameworks, and Strategies includes Nigeria's updated Nationally Determined Contribution 2021(NDC), Climate change Act 2021, Climate action Tracker etc. Furthermore, it raises the chance of Nigeria to the efficient delivery of adaptation which is of great importance to Nigeria; the question is the leader style should be followed up appropriately, this is because of its described exposure to climate extremes and its marginal greenhouse gas emissions. This implies that mitigation, even though important rates lower than adaptation as a national priority. Similarly, adaptation frameworks in relation to environment and climate change at sub-national levels supersedes the majority of projects developed by the Federal Ministry of Environment, which oversees frameworks and legislation concerning climate change adaptation and other environmental concerns, even at local government implemented projects. Hence, at the ministerial level there is a particular style with which governance is led by a politically appointed minister who must provide leadership to and work with public servant (task oriented), in the Nigerian Civil Service at the Directorate level.

A major challenge faced by exhaustively delivering the climate change ambitions in Nigeria is the style of leadership adopted by her leaders who have failed to link the climate situation and feature it in the national discourse. Nigerian's leadership situation is most vulnerable in its implementations of climate measures and limitations especially with regards to a suitable style of leadership because its resource allocation is important to note because climate adaptation is highly and improperly misunderstood.

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Application of the theory

In line with the above assumptions, organizations like United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) and other allied UN bodies responsible for driving the climate change agenda have taken it upon themselves to create massive awareness on a global scale regarding the dangers inherent in the irresponsible use of the environment. The UN has a moral burden on itself to ensure that the environment is protected by promoting the sustainable use of the environment. A disruption in the biosphere and world ecosystem will undermine world peace and security as set out in article 1 of UN Charter (1945), hence the UN's dogged effort to ensure that the environment is not undermined to the point of disrupting world peace and security.

In the light of the above, the UN has the sole responsibility of activating moral norms on individuals, groups, organization and even states to embark on actions that will not undermine the environment. It is this reason that has prompted the UN in 2000 to initiate the MDGs which has eight goals, with MDG 7 ensuring the sustainability of the environment. MDGs 7 major target is to integrate sustainability of the environment through sustainable development principles into country policies and programs and reverse the loss of environmental resources. As the post MDG's program ended in 2015, the development agenda moved to more intricate and detailed goals of 17 Sustainable Development, which were more defined and exact. In this study SDG 13 views closely empirical discuss in which its targets is further broken down into five smaller sub-targets. Furthermore, societies, group and organisation alongside the United Nation Framework On Climate Change Conference (UNFCCC) in Paris is soliciting to correct poor environmental practices in participants and non-believers of the environment who do not have strong belief in proenvironmental norm activation, to strengthen a reawakening in persons, groups and organizations who have poor belief in proenvironmental actions and to activate in those who worked assiduously by creating awareness and education to non-believers on the unsustainable conditions of the environment and its attendant consequences posing a threat to the planet, so that their actions would prevent these consequences which formulate an agreement on protocols, with legal instruments in binding agreement on outcomes with lawful force that apply to all Parties to the Convention, which is to provide a framework for the strengthening of international actions to mitigate climate change.

4.1.2 Challenges of climate change and Nigerias NDC

The challenges of climate change are enormous compared to its consequences. Nigeria is exposed to a vast use of fossil fuels and it has a huge effect on the amount of emission the country emits. In Nigeria, Greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions are the atmospheric gases responsible for causing global warming and climatic change – they are critical to understanding and addressing the climate crisis. Power generation through electricity also is major challenge because heat generated by the burning of fossil fuels. With the natural occurrence of most GHG's, human activities have also been leading to a problematic increase in the amount of GHG emitted and their concentration in the atmosphere in Nigeria. These challenges of climate change asks important questions as to how exactly do GHG emissions warm the planet and what can we do about it? And what are the major greenhouse gases in Nigeria? Carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane and nitrous oxide are the major GHGs. CO₂ stays in the atmosphere for up to 1,000 years, methane for around a decade and nitrous oxide for approximately 120 years. Measured over a 20-year period, methane is 80 times more potent than CO₂ in causing global warming, while nitrous oxide is 280 times more potent. (Hinicio, 2022)

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The submission of Nigerian's five year Nationally Determined Contribution summarily proves that transparent, competent and periodical report should prompt national government, in supporting environmental movement by supporting the freedom of nature's ability to strive. The efforts we make through improving educational awareness, environmental education with the help of institutionalizing the capacity to propagate climate change mitigation, adaptation, impact has the way to the reduction in early warning signs on climate issues in addressing the challenges of climate change. (IPCC 2013). Despite an initial dip in global GHG emissions due to COVID-19, the United Nations Environment Program's latest Emissions Gap Report (EGR) expects a strong rebound in 2021, indicating that emissions are expected to be only slightly lower than the record levels of 2019.(Niklas Hagelberg, 2023)

United Nations Environmental Program's Climate Change Coordinator said "The climate emergency demands action from all of us. We need to get to net zero greenhouse gas emissions by 2050 and everyone has a role to play" Although, in Nigeria, coal, oil and natural gas continue to power many parts of the country, Carbon remains the main element in these fuels, and when they're burned to generate electricity, power transportation provide heat, and produce CO₂, a colorless, odorless gas. Oil and gas extraction, coal mining and waste landfills account for 55 per cent of human-caused methane emissions.

In Nigeria, approximately 32 per cent of human-caused methane emissions are attributable to cows, sheep and other ruminants that ferment food in their stomachs. Manure decomposition is another agricultural source of the gas, as is rice cultivation. Here in Nigeria, Human-caused nitrous oxide emissions largely arise from agriculture practices. (Singh, *et al*, 1997). Bacteria in soil and water naturally convert nitrogen into nitrous oxide, but fertilizer use and run-off add to this process by putting more nitrogen into the environment. Rice cultivation by Nigerian farmers is a major source of methane emissions, as is animal. (Räthzel, *et al* 2018).

This increased concentration, in turn, can lead to adverse effects on climate. Effects include increases in the frequency and intensity of extreme weather events – including flooding, droughts, coastal waste waters and dry winds – that affects millions of people and cause trillions in economic losses. The Emissions Gap Report found that if we do not halve annual GHG emissions by 2030, it will be very difficult to limit global warming to 1.5°C compared to pre-industrial levels by the end of the century. (Tosun, & Leininger, 2017).

Based on current unconditional pledges made by Nigeria to reduce emissions, the world is on a path to see global warming of 2.7 degree Celsius by the end of the century compared to pre-industrial levels. "Human-caused greenhouse gas emissions endanger human and environmental health," (Mark Radka, 2023) Chief of United Nations Environmental Program's Energy and Climate Branch. He said "the impacts of climate change will become more widespread and severed without strong climate action."(UN.ORG, 2023).

4.1.6 Nigerian's NDC mitigated domestic environmental challenges, 2012-2022?

In Nigeria, NDC's efforts to mitigate domestic environmental challenges into national policies, strategies and planning are paving way towards adopting green practices, President Bola Ahmed Tinubu, has made plans to address climate related issues in his present tenure and he hopes to achieve this through his robust environmental initiative towards restoring Nigerians green economy back. But as it stance not much has been said yet about it, the then President Muhammad Buhari sign the Climate Change Act Bill in 2021 bringing the country to an updated version of an active status, of having addressed domestic environmental challenges through transparent

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report of clear definitive plans to reduce GHG emissions. Even though Nigeria has a connection to the kanji grid, she still faces prolong and frequent blackouts mainly often due to low gas supply and shortages of power plant. From the Climate Action Tracker, the government has declared this decade to be the “Decade of Gas” with plans of continuing to invest in gas, infrastructure which comes with it the risks of stranded assets and locking away the energy sector into carbon intensive infrastructure when is it supposed to be investing in even-cheaper renewables.

As the 17th largest natural gas producer in the world, Nigeria is currently struggling to attract investment in recent years. The progress Nigeria has made in reducing gas flaring is still a significant source of emissions along with escape methane emissions in the gas supply chain. What we should be asking is that should Nigeria really be interrogating its own NDCs in mitigating climate change? In November 2021, the then president passed the bill on climate change act seeking to reach low greenhouse gas emission green sustainable growth by setting aside a frame work or target to reach net zero by 2050 and 2070. Nigerians national climate action plan is a determined effort to deal with the current Nigerian predicament of climate change by arresting the necessary policies set aside to curtail the excesses of individual lifestyles, industrial emissions, carbon emissions. The Nigerian national climate action plan to cut emissions and to adapt to climate impacts which is summarily why the NDC was established to enforce countries targets for mitigating greenhouse gases emissions that cause climate change through adapting to climate impacts. Defining how to reach this target is the crux of the plan and to establish systems to monitor and verify progress so it stays on track. Since the money given to finance climate crises is important in implementing the plans, Advocates of the environment through climate active Nature Riders, pro – environmentalist and its NDCs are aiming higher to more sustainable development, greener transformative shifts.

4.1.7 To determine if the resources needed by the Nigerian state sufficiently met its Nationally Determined Contribution, 2012-2022?

Nigeria needs sufficient amount of resources to meet its Nationally Determined Contribution, the question is does Nigeria have the finances to afford resources to adequately sustain it as a state? Nigeria runs a gas economy which is widely prevalent, and the efficiency of the power sector has dwindled down to the drain. Oil and gas sector in the country plays a significant role in the Nigerian economy, especially as gas is singled out as a major commodity used to further sustain Nigerian’s industrial development which has remained mainstream in the energy sector, National Development Plan, (2021).

Due to the recession experienced in Nigeria in 2016, the Nigerian government redirected its focus on positioning the oil and gas sector to contribute to the economic restoration between 2017 and 2020. This led to establishing modular refineries to increase local refining capacity. The Nigerian government supported and encouraged the development of these modular refineries by approving the importation of duty equipment. Due to the unstable prices of global crude oil, the oil and gas sectors have been challenged by the domestic production level. Several constraints have hindered the Nigerian oil and gas industry to fully reach its potential, these include: inadequate infrastructure, high exploration and cost of production, weak legal framework, irregular gas supply, pipeline vandalism and non-functional refineries etc. Vandalism is a persistent challenge, as seen in the first quarter of 2024 alone, in which there have been five significant vandalism incidents, which are: disrupted transmission operations, necessitating emergency repairs and in some cases, complete tower reconstruction of transmission

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line replacement. This called for heightened community support and vigilance in protecting transmission infrastructure. NDP, (2021)

Energy just like the gas sector plays a critical role to Nigeria's overall economic development and industrialization ambition in powering Nigeria's economy, enhancing its competitiveness and ensuring good quality of life for its teeming 200 million residents. Natural gas is a current mix driven mostly by hydropower despite an abundance of renewable energy sources such as solar and wind energy. Indeed Nigeria's industrialization objectives cannot be realized without reliable and affordable access to energy. The most significant reform is the Electricity Power Sector Reform Act in 2005. Having witnessed a series of reforms with the development of roadmaps and plans, these reforms enabled private companies to participate in distributing electricity, generating it and transmitting it to develop competitive electricity markets, enforce performance standards and to eliminate the long-term monopoly by the defunct National Electric Power Authority (NEPA). Consequently, NEPA further dissolved into six power generating companies, eleven distribution companies and one transmission company. Even though Nigeria is blessed with alternative energy sources such as wind, solar, and biomass, Nigeria has not yet maximized these energy potentials to their full use. In regards to this plan, the Nigerian government will prioritize efforts to maximize these alternative energy sources to increase energy per capita so as to spur industrialization.

As reiterated earlier, Nigeria's power sector is lagging behind with a per capita power consumption of 144kWh, as against South Africa's 4,200kWh and Ghana's 351kWh. This is far behind the average of 6,022kWh for the European Union and 483kWh for Sub Saharan Africa, even as Nigeria is assumed to be the biggest economy in Africa. The power sector in Nigeria has witnessed a series of reforms from 2001 till date with the most important being the Electric Power Sector Reform Act (EPSRA) 2005.

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5.1 Summary of Findings

The study found that United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 13 on Climate Action addressed the challenges of climate change, And that Nigeria's Nationally Determined Contribution mitigated domestic environmental challenges. The study further found that the reason the NDC did not mitigate domestic environmental challenges lies in its poor implementation by the Nigerian government. Based on the contingency theory, different leadership styles has structured the Nigerian government in choosing to implement her policies in different styles different from every other way, this has made issues regarding the environment seem to be addressed from a different point of view. Nigeria basically lacks the essential resources needed to meet its Nationally Determined Contributions, even though Nigeria has committed to conditionally reduce emissions with the help of foreign aid. She still needs strong environmental policies to draw the attention of Nigeria to the deplorable situation of climate change in the country.

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5.2 Conclusion

One of the targets of SDG13 is to pursue the integration of climate change measures and solutions into national and global policies. In conclusion, Nigeria needs to establish an environmental research institute needed to improve education and awareness about climate change, and to inculcate in individuals, groups and societies the knowledge of environmental perceptions. Since the reduction of GHG emission has taken a toll in year past. this study advices that Nigeria adjust through its national government in making sure that the government is pressured into harnessing environmental laws and policies and for proper implementation of climate related hazards in the country.

5.3 Recommendations

It is of keynote importance to accept that significant implementation of environmental policies play a critical role in various climate change related issues faced globally, it is therefore necessary for administrative governments in Nigeria to wake up to the process of developing and implementing climate ambitious policies, in other to harness more effectively the reduction of carbon emission cuts. Nigerians Nationally Determined reductions concerning climate change should reflect extensively measures in mitigating domestic environmental challenges which is the first step in addressing poor implementation by the Nigerian government. This study recommends amongst others, that Nigeria needs to build strong institutions commissioned to implement environmental laws in Nigeria.

Sustainable Development Goal 13 on Climate action addresses the challenges of Climate Change, 2012- 2022, in firstly adopting and building knowledge and capacity in other to meet climate change this involves creating the enabling manpower and awareness of environmentally prone related hazards. The Resources needed by the Nigerian State met its Nationally Determined contribution for the period 2012-2022. The country should include viable institutions established by the government to cut down emissions. Nigeria's Nationally Determined Contribution mitigated domestic environmental challenges in 2012-2022. By reducing its conditional commitment of GHG to 47 % with a pledge to reducing 30% by 2030.

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